

Magnetic-responsive materials tailored to enhance the cascade of bone regeneration and immune response

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ABSTRACT

Aging, diseases, or immunodeficiency's can significantly impair the physiological regenerative process and the endogenous regenerative potential of bone tissue. Intensive research focuses on developing scaffolds that fill bone gaps while promoting cellular interaction and guiding tissue regeneration. Biomimicry is today widely acknowledged as a leading concept to develop novel approaches based on biomimetic materials to fabricate smart devices with advanced performance and multiple bio-functionalities. In the pursuit of designing smart devices for more efficient and personalized therapies, magnetic materials are eliciting growing interest due to the possibility of direct cell stimulation by magnetic fields or even for developing novel tools for the *on-demand* activation of implanted magnetic devices. There is a growing focus on understanding the impact of immune responses and the role of immunomodulators in the healing and regeneration of bone tissue.

The relevance of biomimicry, immune and tissue responses to magnetic scaffolds and stimulation, alongside an examination of the limitations of existing bone substitutes in the market is highlighted. Biomimetic and magnetically activated scaffolds hold promise as innovative tools in addressing bone tissue diseases and promoting regeneration by effectively engaging in cellular and immunological responses.

1. Introduction

Bone defects are among the main causes of reduced life quality due to trauma, diseases (e.g. cancer, osteoporosis-related fractures, congenital bone malformations), aging, intense sport activity, obesity, or dysfunction. The natural process of bone repair is able to regenerate fractures, although bone tissue cannot self-regenerate in the case of large sized “critical” lesions [1,2]. Every year in United States, about \$2.5 billion of dollars in replacements of bone defects are expended. Although, with the increasing of life expectancy the costs of bone replacement procedures are predicted to steadily grow [3]. The implantation of autografts (i.e. bone transplantation from one part to another part of the same body), allografts (i.e. bone transplantation from donor of the same species) and xenografts (i.e. from other species) were the first used therapeutic approaches in bone tissue replacement. Autografts, to date still major

choice of surgeons, are defined as “gold standard”; however, various drawbacks such as increased morbidity, pain, bone graft loss/resorption, lack of vascularisation, reduced availability and high cost [4–6] make such a solution quite ineffective. Therefore, for decades, intensive research is dedicated to the development of synthetic bone grafts with actual regenerative ability. The occurrence of degenerative dysmetabolic bone diseases, as well as ageing, can strongly impair effective bone regeneration, particularly the age-related cell senescence affects cell viability, metabolism, and the overall endogenous potential [7].

Osteosarcoma and osteoporosis are among the most relevant bone diseases affecting young and elderly individuals, respectively. Surgery and chemotherapy are the most used standard treatments in osteosarcoma with an improved 5-year overall survival to 66 % of cases. About osteosarcoma, the most relevant concerns are related to the incomplete killing or removal of cancer cells, the increasing resistance to standard

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therapies, the adverse side effects on the patients and the resurgence of the tumour, highlighting the need on developing more effective therapies [8–10]. The main challenge is to offer novel solutions that in one way promote the removal of the remained tumour cells and in another way promote tissue regeneration. On the other hand, osteoporosis is one of the most common systemic skeletal diseases in people over 50 years old, and frequently detected at severe stage. The aging impairs the dynamic natural process of bone repair thus exposing to osteoporosis-related fractures, which can generate high disability and remarkable healthcare costs with expected increasing to 24.8 % until 2034. Therefore, there is a treatment gap (71 %, 2019) in women that do not receive treatment after fracture, that can be potentially serious, thus contributing to increased relative mortality [11]. Current treatments, such as medicines overfilling during bone remodelling, have limited therapeutic exposure, and several side effects are reported [12]. Concerns on treating osteosarcoma, osteoporosis or simply to regenerate bone tissue from fracture, effective therapies are needed. For example, the currently commercialised synthetic bone substitutes are mainly composed of demineralised bone or high crystalline hydroxyapatite and frequently (Table 1) unmet clinical needs, as: i) difficult to develop bone substitutes associating bioactivity and bioresorbability; ii) difficult to design bone substitutes to reduce the cancer cells and then effectively to restore bone tissue or used to fill the gap in osteoporotic bone; iii) difficult to address patients affected by reduced endogenous potential. These can represent a lack on following the bone tissue growth of young or elderly patients making the treatment difficult and frequently the desired bone restoration is not achieved.

The increased life expectancy and the high incidence of fractures or diseases-related fractures in elderly open a challenge on developing more effective and personalized therapies. The combination of cells, scaffolds, and growth factors are the typical bone tissue engineering research approach to restore bone tissue. However, several concerns have been highlighted on moving from this research to clinical practise, such as i) long years of research and associated costs; ii) need of approval by ever stricter regulatory issues; iii) very low percentage of systems that are tested *in vitro* and *in vivo* move forward to clinical practise. To this regard, scientists are looking to cell-free routes, mainly on synthetic bone substitutes featuring inherent high regenerative ability. It is increasing the interest on scaffolds with close mimicry (i.e. chemical, structural, mechanical, biological) with the bone tissue that can be able to instruct cells and guide them to physiological metabolic activity towards new bone tissue formation and regrowth, that can be considered as a “golden” conceptual approach. Physical stimulation (as mechanical, electrical, or magnetic) is attracting increasing interest because they are not invasive, can be externally applicable, and are safe, in respect to drugs and growth factors, and can be suggested for patients with reduced endogenous potential [51].

In this review, an overview on biomechanical features of bone tissue, approaches for scaffolds fabrication and tissue response to scaffolds, as well as the use of biomimicry strategies to regenerate bone tissue are discussed. Nevertheless, special focus will be given to magnetic materials and novel biomimetic magnetic materials that can stimulate the cell activity and modulate the tissue regeneration cascade and immune system even in absence of external magnetic fields. Magnetic materials combined with magnetic signalling can represent a new cell-free routes boosting metabolic activity towards bone tissue regeneration and immune system stimulation.

2. Bone composition, structure, and physical properties

Bone presents an hierarchical structure with unique mechanical properties, and remodelling capabilities. It is constituted by several cell types (osteoblasts, osteocytes, osteoclasts), extracellular matrix (containing crystalline hydroxyapatite), collagen type I, non-collagenous proteins, regulatory proteins, growth factors and water [52]. Structurally, bone is organized in seven hierarchical levels, from nanoscale to

macroscale [53] (Fig. 1). At the nanoscale, calcium phosphate ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$; 69–80 wt%), type I collagen (17–20 wt%), non-collagenous proteins (e.g. sialoprotein, osteonectin, osteopontin), growth factors, water and cells [54–56]. Osteoblasts, derived from mesenchymal stem cells, produce the extracellular matrix and differentiate into osteocytes, while osteoclasts are involved in resorption and remodelling [57]. In the second level appear the mineralised collagen fibrils, whereas the arrays of mineralised collagen fibrils are defined as the third level. Various fibrils patterns arrays (e.g. parallel arrays, woven arrangements, plywood-like structures or radial arrays) and osteons are respectively showed at fourth and fifth level. The sixth level is constituted by cortical and trabecular bone. Cortical bone is dense, with low porosity (pore size: 1–100 μm and porosity: 5–10 wt%) and high mechanical strength (Young’s moduli of about 17 GPa). In contrast, trabecular bone has high porosity (pore size: 200–400 μm and porosity: 75–95 wt%), providing a supportive network for cells and blood vessels, however with lower mechanical strength (Young’s moduli of about 1 GPa). Finally, the entire bone is considered the seventh level [53].

Aging, the use of pharmaceuticals, and diseases can all impact bone tissue porosity, increasing the risk of fracture. With age, trabecular bone is first impacted and can contribute to osteoporosis at skeletal sites [58]. Bone physical properties differs between individuals due to several parameters, such as apparent density, histology, collagen composition and content, orientation, and bonding of the collagen fibers and mineral, composition of the cement lines, as well as accumulation of microcracks in the bone matrix and around osteons [57].

3. Biomimetic strategies for bone tissue engineering

Materials scientists have been developing bone-regenerating scaffolds to mimic the physical, chemical and biological features of bone to support regeneration [61–63]. However, bone is a complex tissue that presents several challenges in its repair [64]. An equilibrium between resorption and formation is needed to ensure a mechanically strong and healthy bone after the remodelling cycle. If the healing process is inappropriate, the remodelling process can cause pathological conditions that lead to the development of bone diseases [65]. Therefore, healing fractures caused by bone diseases like osteoporosis, osteoarthritis, and osteosarcoma continues to pose a significant clinical challenge [66]. As a result, natural or synthetic-based scaffolds have been developed as a strategy to balance cell activity while minimizing side effects and restoring bone tissue.

3.1. Bone scaffolds approaches

Scaffold fabrication involves conventional and additive bio-manufacturing technologies [3,67–69]. Conventional methods are simple and versatile, however it is difficult to control scaffolds architecture, resulting in poor pore shape and interconnectivity. Freeze-drying process is one of the most used conventional techniques for the development of natural-based scaffolds (i.e. collagen, gelatin, alginate, silk). Many researchers have accessed to freeze-drying process to develop collagen-based scaffolds [1] or protein related scaffolds that are enriched with RGD motifs, which provide key signalling for cells to activate the regenerative cascade [70]. Electrohydrodynamic (i.e. electrospinning, electrospray) strategies can be used in this context to generate continuous or range gradients, resulting in nano-fibers/particles manufacture [71,72]. Additive bio-manufacturing technologies are investigated to guarantee accurate, reproducible, and customised scaffolds fabrication. Tailored scaffolds with defined size, shape and porosity can be fabricated by different 3D printing strategies, as laser stereolithography, selective laser sintering, extrusion-based printing, or inkjet-based printing [69,73,74]. Customised structures can be 3D printed in a wide range of natural or synthetic biomaterials, as well as assembled with cells or signalling factors, to create more efficient scaffold, ready to be implanted [69]. Bone substitutes need to mimic the

Table 1
Examples of commercialised bone substitutes.

Company	Grafts	Composition	Type of structure	Applications	Ref.
Striker, USA	Allograft Bio implants	Demineralized and mineralized bone from animals	Putty, sponge, particulate, and structural forms	Craniomaxillofacial	[13]
	HydroSet, Injectable Bone Substitute	Self-setting calcium phosphate bone substitute	Easily injectable	Neurosurgery	
DepuySynthes, UK	DBX™ Material	Demineralised bone matrix from human donors in a sodium hyaluronate carrier	Injectable	Bone lesion	[14]
	NORIAN™ Reinforced Fast Set Putty	Reinforced fibers, sodium hyaluronate based solution	Moldable, biocompatible	Bony contours of the craniofacial skeleton	[15]
	chronOS™ Granules and Preforms System	β-tricalcium phosphate material, autologous bone marrow introduces blood cells, growth factors and osteoprogenitor cells	Porous structure	Bone	[16]
	chronOS™ Inject Bone Void Filler	Calcium phosphate bone substitute	Injectable	Cancellous or cortico-cancellous bone	[17]
	chronOS™ Strip System	Granules with a defined, uniform pore structure imbedded in a matrix of poly(lactide-co-ε-caprolactone)	Granules in matrix	Bone	[18]
Integra Life Sciences, USA	Allograft Wedge System	Processed human allograft tissue	Sponge	Bone grafting for osteotomy corrections	[19]
	PRO-DENSE™ Injectable Regenerative Graft	Synthetic composite of calcium sulfate and calcium phosphate	Injectable	Bone	[20]
Wright focused excellence, USA	3Demin®	100 % human demineralized cortical bone fiber, contains growth factors	Different types of flexible templates	Bone	[21]
	OsteoSelect PLUS	Demineralized cortical chips (1–4 mm) with OsteoSelect formulation	Handling structure	Bone graft in spinal procedures	[22]
Xtant medical, USA	OsteoSponge	Demineralized cancellous bone	Scaffold	Bone	[23]
	OsteoSponge SC	Demineralized cancellous bone	Scaffold	Pathology of damaged subchondral bone of the articulating joints	[24]
	OsteoVive	Cells and scaffold composed of microparticulate cortical, cancellous, and demineralized cortical allograft bone with particle size, 100–300 μm.	Cells and microparticles	Bone	[25]
	OsteoWrap	100 % human cortical bone demineralized	Handling characteristics can be easily sized with a scalpel or scissors, and it may be sutured in place.	Spinal, neurological, cranio-maxillofacial, reconstructive, and general orthopaedic surgical procedures.	[26]
Arthrex, Inc., USA	OSferion	100 % β-tricalcium phosphate	Porous 3D structure	Osteotomia	[27]
	INNOTERE 3D	Calcium phosphate molded forms	3D printed scaffolds	Fill osseous damage and support osteosynthesis	[28]
	INNOTERE Paste-CPC	Calcium phosphate	Injectable, self-setting cement	Bone	[29]
NovaBone, USA	Quickset™	Calcium phosphate	Cement	Bone	[30]
	NovaBone	Calcium phospho-silicate	Scaffold, injectable, cement	Bone	[31]
BonAlive® biomaterials LTD, Finland	BonAlive® granules	Bioactive glass S53P4 (53 % SiO ₂ , 23 % Na ₂ O, 20 % CaO, 4 % P ₂ O ₅)	Granules	Cranio-maxillofacial Orthopaedics (Ortho)	[32]
	BonAlive® putty	Osteostimulative S53P4 bioactive glass granules and a water-soluble synthetic binder (Si, Na, Ca, P)	Injectable	Bony voids and gaps	
SigmaGraft Biomaterials, USA	InterOss®	Natural hydroxyapatite bone grafting material derived from Australia bovine bone (BSE free).	Granule form	Bone	[33]
	InterOss® Syringe	Bone grafting material: hydroxyapatite, derived from Australia bovine bone (BSE free).	Chemically and structurally comparable to mineralized human bone	Bone	[34]
	Hydroxyapatite; beta-tricalcium phosphate; Biphasic calcium phosphate	Hydroxyapatite; beta-tricalcium phosphate; Biphasic calcium phosphate	Various bone-graft substitute products	Bone	[35]
	InterCollagen®	Porcine pericardium derived resorbable collagen membrane (type I and type III)	Membrane	Periodontal and/or dental surgical procedures	[36]
	InterOss® Collagen	Bone graft with granules (250—1000 μm) and 10 % porcine collagen type I	Scaffold	Regenerative dental applications	[37]
	InterOss® Collagen Anorganic bone composite Plug	Type I collagen	Block	Regenerative dental applications	[38]
	Orthofix	TRINITY ELITE TRINITY Evolution	Allograft Allograft: cancellous bone with viable osteogenic and osteoprogenitor cells retained within the matrix and a demineralized cortical bone component	Handling structure Handling structure	Musculoskeletal defects Bone
	Collage	Synthetic bone graft substitute product (80 % highly purified beta-tricalcium phosphate and 20 % type-I collagen)	Scaffold	Bone	
	AlloQuent structural allograft	100 % cortical allograft planks	Scaffold	Cervical and lumbar allograft procedures	

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Company	Grafts	Composition	Type of structure	Applications	Ref.
Citagenix Inc., Canada	Raptos	Allograft cancellous irradiated bone granules	Bone granules	Bone regeneration	[40]
	Citagenix	Allograft tissue products	Struts, rings and blocks	Skeletal repairs	[41]
	Accell Connexus®	Demineralized bone matrix	Granules	Bone	[42]
	OrthoBlast® II	Demineralized bone matrix with cancellous bone	Scaffold	Bone	
	DynaGraft® II	Demineralized bone matrix in a poloxamer reverse phase medium	Scaffold	Bone	
	C-Graft putty™ or C-Blast Putty™	Demineralized Bone Matrix putty with Carboxymethylcellulose and with Cancellous bone chips	Hydrogel	Bone	[43]
	SKaffold Calcium Phosphate Cement	Calcium phosphate	Cement	Filling bony defects in cancellous bone	[44]
Heraeus Holding GmbH, Germany	INTEGRA MOZAIK OSTEOCONDUCTIVE SCAFFOLD	Collagen type I (20 %) and beta-tricalcium phosphate (80 %)	Moldable scaffold	Bone	
	HERAFILL® BEADS G	Calcium Sulphate; Calcium carbonate; Gentamicin	Bone filler	Resorbable bone void filling material with the benefit of infection prevention	[45]
	OSTEOPAL® V COPAL® G + C	Zirconium dioxide Calcium carbonate with gentamicin and clindamycin	Bone cement Bone cement	Spinal surgery Anchoring prosthetic implants	[46] [47]
Graftys®, France	Graftys® QuickSet	Calcium Phosphate and HydroxyPropylMethylCellulose (HMPC) and phosphate-based aqueous solution	Bone cement	Fracture repair, extremities or pelvis, complex fractures, joint arthroplasty, tibial osteotomy	[48]
Geistlich Pharma AG, Switzerland	Graftys® HBS Orthoss®	Calcium phosphate Highly purified bovine bone mineral	Injectable bone graft Scaffolds	Bone Bone voids filling for reconstruction of orthopaedics and in spinal surgery	[49]
	Orthoss® Collagen	Highly purified natural bone mineral combined with native collagen	Scaffolds	Orthopaedic bone regeneration	
botiss biomaterials GmbH, Germany	Maxgraft®; bonebuilder; maxgraft® bonering; maxgraft® cortico; Innovative biphasic calcium phosphate	Bone from human donors (multi-organ donors or femoral heads of living donors)	Scaffolds	Bone	[50]
	maxresorb® inject	60 % hydroxyapatite and 40 % beta-tricalcium phosphate	Matrix of interconnected pores and with very high porosity (80 %), with pore sizes (200–800 µm)	Bone	
	collacone® max	Water-based gel; hydroxyapatite nanoparticles with small maxresorb granules particles (size 15–50 nm)	Injectable bone graft	Bone	
	collacone® max	Synthetic granules and porcine collagen fibres – biphasic calcium phosphate granules (60 % hydroxyapatite; 40 % β-tricalcium phosphate)	Scaffold	Bone	

Fig. 1. The hierarchical composition of bone tissue.

Adapted from [54,59,60] .

bone microenvironment, including mechanical, biochemical and electromechanical queues [75,76]. Porosity facilitates vascularization, nutrient transport, and host integration, while degradation rates must align with bone growth dynamic [3,63,77,78].

Recent approaches include magnetic scaffolds. Previous research has shown that magnetic scaffolds can improve bone regeneration both on their own and in combination with magnetic field application, with positive effects on biochemical pathways [79]. However, creating 3D fibrous magnetic scaffolds remains a challenge for broadening the applicability of magnetic fibers in bone tissue engineering [79] (Fig. 2).

In nature, a plethora of elements composed of undefined dimensions, architectures, functions or materials, are being relevant as an inspiration to produce new devices for tissue engineering applications [70,80]. Alginate, chitin or marine coral can be extracted from algae, crustaceans' exoskeletons and *porites species* sea urchins, respectively and are examples of natural sources to be applied on bone tissue regeneration [81,82]. Rattan wood is another example of natural source that through chemical and physical processes can meet the desired mechanical properties and complex hierarchical structure of bone tissue [54–56], presenting 85 % of porosity with porous about 240 μm (Fig. 1). Therefore, good cell viability in presence of MG63 osteoblasts-like cells was obtained and bone was formed into the channels of apatite scaffolds obtained by biomorphic transformation of Rattan scaffold without inflammatory response after implantation in adult New Zealand White disease-free rabbits [83–85].

A special emphasis is given to the biomineralisation process. This process replicates the natural deposition of low crystalline carbonate hydroxyapatite (HAp) and with trace of foreign ions (e.g. Na, Cl, F, K^+ , Sr^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+}) on collagen fibrils, producing nanostructured materials with bone-like properties [1,53,70,86].

The regeneration process of bone tissue is mediated by biomineralisation process, where at the nanoscale level, non-stoichiometric carbonate hydroxyapatite nanocrystals (plate-shaped, 100–50 nm \times 25 nm in size, 1.5–4 nm thick) are heterogeneously nucleated onto non-mineralised organic macromolecules (i.e. type I collagen, \sim 300 nm long, \sim 1.5 nm in diameter) with preferential orientation along the *c* axis and parallel to collagen fibrils and organised in a periodic, staggered array along the fibrils [56,65,70,87,88] (Fig. 1).

The self-assembly of the collagen fibrils and the formation of crystals of the mineral phase are phenomena governed by various control mechanisms activated by the same structure of the protein macromolecule thanks to specific pH conditions and ions concentration

[84,89,90].

Several researchers have been investigated the biomineralisation process with non-collagenous proteins or collagen. Hence, they showed that hydroxyapatite nucleation on polypeptides can be improved by hydrophobic alkyl tails covalently bonded to thick hydrophilic peptide head groups with phosphorylated serine, while bone cells adhesion and chemotactic response was improved by adding RGD motifs to the biomaterials [91–93]. On the other hand, an innovative *in lab* synthesis was investigated to develop bone-like materials made of collagen type I mineralized with hydroxyapatite nanocrystals and was denominated as bio-inspired biomineralisation process. Acidic natural type I collagen in form of nanofibrils was mineralised with hydroxyapatite nanocrystals by mediation of neutralisation process. Then, the addition of foreign ions into HAp lattice (e.g. Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+}) can improve the osteoinductivity, bioresorbability, immune-modulation, antibacterial properties, as well as to control the crystallization degree of hydroxyapatite nanocrystals [94,95]. During the biomineralisation process, carbonate ions might occupy the phosphate site of hydroxyapatite lattice (B type position) and can be beneficial for cell adhesion and instruct the formation of new bone tissue [84,89,96]. The presence of specific functional groups on collagen surface induces the crystal size and the specific orientation of apatite nuclei in respect to the collagen fibrils achieving the bone-like properties in hybrid composites. In the final hybrids, good inter connected porosity and adequate pore size can be obtained by tailoring the freeze-drying process; while biomechanical properties can be stabilised by using crosslinking methods [97].

Bio-inspired biomineralisation process is highlighted as relevant advance on biomaterials science with the regard to obtain biomimetic biomaterials; in particular, by varying the mineralisation extent, graded scaffolds for osteochondral applications or periodontal regions can be developed.

Maioregen (Finceramica, Italy) is an example of commercialised scaffold for osteochondral regeneration. It is composed of three different layers and mimics the different zones of osteochondral region (i.e. cartilaginous tissue, tide-mark and subchondral bone structure). The potentiality of Maioregen was proved by clinical studies, with progressive regeneration of osteo-cartilaginous defects (Finceramica, Italy) [98]. An innovative xenofree biomaterial composed of recombinant peptide based on human collagen type I (RCP) enriched with RGD motif is commercially available as Cellnest™ (Fujifilm Manufacturing Europe B.V. (The Netherlands)) and has been investigated for bone tissue regeneration. Researchers found that RCP matrix could be mineralized

Fig. 2. Biomimetic strategies for Bone Tissue Engineering.

with hydroxyapatite or ions-doped hydroxyapatite and new devices with potentiality and outstanding properties for bone tissue applications can be developed [1,99–101].

3.2. Bioactive properties of hydroxyapatite and ions substitution

Bone tissue is composed of non-stoichiometric hydroxyapatite phase presenting calcium and hydroxyl deficiency with various ion substitutions and vacancies, thus resulting in Ca/P molar ratio different from the stoichiometric hydroxyapatite (1.67) [53,54]. Several ions are presented in physiological environment and the low crystallinity is affected by the presence of these ions into hydroxyapatite lattice (e.g. CO_3^{2-} , Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , SiO_4^{4-} and HPO_4^{2-}) and the typical ion substitutions are: F^- to Cl^- or OH^- position; carbonate for phosphate or OH^- position, while, Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Na^+ for Ca^{2+} position [89,102–104]. CO_3^{2-} ions mainly substitute phosphate (B type position) and, in a lesser extent, OH^- ions (A type position). Particularly, B-type substitution is typical of young and immature bone; indeed B-carbonation enhances structural disorder in the mineral phase lattice and consequently increases its chemical reactivity and ability to be remodelled. High amount of CO_3^{2-} ions in non-apatitic phase and more disordered domains in young bone are presented. This prevalence favours the ions reservoir that are relevant for cell activity, as well as for bone healing and regeneration [1,61,84,89,95].

Inspired by the relevant role of HAp and the different ions, it has been investigated as an excellent candidate to be used in the regeneration of damaged bone tissue. Synthetic hydroxyapatite presents high biocompatibility, bioactivity, non-toxicity and osteoinductive properties with lack of any immune responses [84,105]. Wet chemical precipitation, sol–gel synthesis, co-precipitation, hydrothermal synthesis, rapid or continuous precipitation from solution, thermal-decomplexing batch method, are some of the methodologies that are successfully investigated to synthesise HAp [53,106–108].

During the HAp synthesis, various ions (i.e. silicon (Si), strontium (Sr), magnesium (Mg), zinc (Zn) and iron (Fe)) can be added into the apatite lattice with the aim to improve biomimetic, biological, mechanical and antibacterial properties [84,105,109,110]. Magnesium-substituted hydroxyapatite induces adhesion, proliferation and metabolic activation of osteoblasts and osteoclasts, as well as enhance the bone metabolism [111]. The presence of silicon in calcium phosphates improves cartilage growth, osteoblasts activity, as well as enhances bone tissue remodelling and repair [95,112,113], while the presence of carbonate and strontium improves the material dissolution, that facilitate the implant resorption [114]. Strontium and zinc have shown antimicrobial effects. Besides, mechanical performance was enhanced by the use of silicates [106]. Silver and gallium were instead investigated as antibacterial regulator and in the treatment of bone cancer, respectively [61]. Furthermore, the incorporation of iron ions into HAp lattice has steadily increased for the fabrication of magnetically activated scaffolds, as will be later discussed. Table 2 provides an overview of the most relevant ions for bone tissue regeneration and their properties that can effectively be introduced into HAp lattice.

According to recent investigations, multiple ion substitution into HAp lattice can improve antibacterial bioactivity, and enhance osteointegrability, osteogenesis, angiogenesis [85,120,121]. The approach of using foreign ions or multiple ions substitution into HAp lattice could stimulate the bone regenerative cascade. The sequential release of ions can recruit the endogenous cells and can have higher beneficial effect when compared with the use of therapeutic factors (e.g. growth factors), which presents limited bioactivity and can cause severe side effects at higher concentrations [122]. More research is needed to investigate the effect of multiple ions release on bone tissue regeneration, although materials composed of ion substituted HAp already present excellent features for bone tissue applications.

Table 2
Relevant ions for bone tissue regeneration.

Ions	Properties	Ref.
Calcium	Cellular calcium signalling is a key process in the formation and repair of bone; Enhance the proliferation of mesenchymal precursor cells and mature bone cells; Induces the bone synthesis pathways in osteoblasts, through interaction with the calmodulin protein and activation of extracellular-signal regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2) during mechanical stimulation and associated increased fluid shear in the bone; Downstream effects of calcium signalling include activation of the phosphoinositide 3-kinase/protein kinase B (PI3K/Akt) pathways, which supports the continued survival of osteoblasts; Promotes osteoblast proliferation and extracellular matrix (ECM) mineralization.	[115,116]
Phosphorus	Second-most abundant mineral in the human body; Found in nucleic acids, proteins, phospholipids, carbohydrates, and ATP; Role in physiological processes: energy metabolism, cellular signalling, and maintaining cell membrane integrity and acid-base homeostasis; 85 % of phosphorus is presented in the bone, complexed with calcium, in the form of hydroxyapatite; 15 % is found in soft tissue and extracellular fluid; In osteoblasts and pre-osteoblasts, regulates proliferation (partly via an increase in IGF-I), differentiation, and mineralization via the ERK1/2 signalling pathway, and apoptosis through decreasing the mitochondrial transmembrane potential, an effect that is increased by calcium; High concentrations inhibit osteoclastic differentiation and bone resorption activity in a dose-dependent manner, via negative feedback exerted on RANK-RANKL signalling and directly inducing apoptosis in osteoclasts.	[115,116]
Carbonate	Presented in biological apatites (4–8 wt%); Mainly replace phosphates in biological apatite; Can substitute at two sites in the apatite lattice, i.e., the hydroxyl ion position and the phosphate ion position, having A-type and B-type carbonated apatites, respectively, and a platelet morphology that interacts with collagen fibrils; B-type substitution is mainly identified in the bone of the majority of species with the A/B ratio (0.7–0.9); Higher solubility of bone apatite can be ascribed to the smaller crystallite size and higher carbonate concentration.	[53,116]
Magnesium	Induces the solubility of the material at physiological pH; Enhance bone metabolism, enzymatic reactions involved in energy metabolism and synthesis of proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids; Improves osteogenesis; Stimulation of human bone mesenchymal stem cells; Enhance matrix mineralization, osteogenic gene expression, protein expression of collagen type X and growth factors (e.g. VEGF); Decrease the secretion of proinflammatory cytokines (e.g. IL-1b and IL-6); Increase cellular adhesion, spreading, proliferation, alkaline phosphatase activity, matrix mineralization, and osteogenic differentiation <i>in vitro</i> ; Enhance osseointegration <i>in vivo</i> ; Magnesium deficiency: correlated with osteoporosis, negatively influence all skeletal metabolism stages, with consequent inhibition of bone growth, decreased osteoblastic and osteoclastic activities, osteopenia, and bone fragility.	[115,116]
Strontium	Osteogenic differentiation of mesenchymal stem cells by upregulating the expression of osteoblast marker genes (e.g. Runx2, osteonectin (OCN), osteopontin (OPN), bone sialoprotein (BSP), and type 1 collagen); Increase alkaline phosphatase activity and matrix	[115,116]

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Table 2 (continued)

Ions	Properties	Ref.
	mineralization; Upregulates the expression of endogenous BMP-2; Enhances the proliferation and osteogenic differentiation of osteoblastic cells, and inhibits osteoclast activity <i>in vitro</i> ; Promotes bone formation, remodelling and osseointegration <i>in vivo</i> ; Antibacterial properties; Treatment for osteoporosis in the form of strontium ranelate: <i>In vitro</i> , the drug has a dual mode of action, both decreasing bone resorption and increasing bone formation; Increase in osteoblast surfaces, mineral apposition rate, trabecular and cortical bone formation bone mineral density, and lower risk of fracture.	
Zinc	Increase enzyme activity and DNA synthesis; Antibacterial activity; Roles in numerous biological functions: enzymatic activity, nucleic acid metabolism, protein synthesis, preservation of the structures and functions of the membranes and hormonal activity, and the normal growth and development of the skeletal system; Increase of alkaline phosphatase levels.	[115–117]
Silicon	Concentration is increased during early bone calcification, inducing hydroxyapatite precipitation into the matrix; Modulation of homeostasis of collagen and other ECM proteins in bone matrix; Improves osteoblast differentiation and collagen I production in human osteoblast cells; Induces angiogenesis and vascularization; Activates the AMPK/ERK2/3 and PI3K/Akt pathways, which are involved in osteogenesis and angiogenesis.	[115]
Iron	Balanced bone homeostasis needs ideal iron levels; Enrolled in the synthesis of metalloproteins; Forms essential complexes with enzymes, oxidative metabolism, energy production in mitochondria, in non-heme enzymes, elements with storage or iron-transferring function; Development of connective tissue of several neurotransmitters in the brain; Improves the cell physiological functions, as osteoblasts proliferation and remineralization;	[118,119]

4. Novel generation of magnetic hydroxyapatite-based materials

The attempt of using personalised and biomimetic scaffolds is gaining high impact on bone regeneration. Bioactive materials with factual cell-instructive ability, suitable mechanical and magnetic properties, exhibiting physicochemical and ultrastructural mimesis with natural tissues are considered as an elective approach to accomplish the requirements for young and elderly patients [123]. The dynamic function of bone tissue requires suitable bone substitutes that recruit endogenous stem cells to differentiate into specific cells and that helps bone tissue to restore [124]. Because of its similarities to the mineral component of bone, hydroxyapatite is one of the most investigated biomaterials as a bone substitute [125]. But, it lacks antibacterial activity despite its high biocompatibility and osteoconductivity [126]. While iron ions are important in the human body due to their antibacterial bioactivity, they are also a cofactor for many proteins and enzymes involved in critical reactions such as cell division and oxidant protection [127]. Furthermore, iron improves a variety of cellular physiological functions, including osteoblast proliferation and remineralization [118].

4.1. Iron-doped hydroxyapatite (Fe-HA)

Magnetic scaffolds composed of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONS) are reported that positively induce the bone healing, however their long-term toxicity effect in the human body is unclear [128]. Some authors defend that magnetite nanoparticles

present low stability [129,130] and tends to aggregate due to the strong magnetic dipole–dipole attractions. Colloidal dispersion and biocompatibility can be improved by modifying the surface charge and surface topography with hydrophilic polymers (e.g. dextran or chitosan) [131] or with bovine serum albumin, siloxanes and citric acid [129,132].

Therefore, a new concept on development of bioactive and bioresorbable biomimetic materials with intrinsic magnetization has been investigated. As referred in the section 3.3, HAp has crystal structure that allows the incorporation of different ions. Recent studies have shown the possibility of doping HAp lattice with $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ions, during the neutralization process, by partial replacement of the two crystal sites of calcium and iron doped-hydroxyapatite (Fe-HA) is obtained [84].

Previous research already shown that Fe-HA has higher bioactivity than pure hydroxyapatite [133]. Others have also claimed that Fe-HA can be useful for bone regeneration and joint infection treatment due to its blood compatibility, increased antibacterial activity, and ability to prolong drug release [134]. Despite the benefits presented, and notwithstanding the fact that hydroxyapatite-based nanomaterials have been among the most studied biomaterials, their ecotoxicological effects are largely unknown [135].

Recently, Pnya et. al., (2022) [136] used chemical precipitation to create an iron doped hydroxyapatite/graphitic carbon nitride (Fe-HAP/GCN) composite with varying iron concentrations. As a result, increasing the concentration of the iron (0.0.1, 0.05, 0.10, and 0.50 M) precursor had a significant effect on apatite growth, highlighting its potential for bone tissue regeneration.

Moreover, Fe-HA has superparamagnetic properties and its properties can be optimised with the synthesis conditions and their effect in the presence of the cells can be tailored with magnetic fields [83,84,89,113,137]. The magnetic phase has single magnetic domain (crystals < 50 nm) that is solely activated in the presence of magnetic fields and can enhance the regenerative cascade [101,138,139]. *In vitro* and *in vivo* tests indicated no cytotoxic effect of Fe-HA in presence of rabbit osteoblasts cells after 24 h of cell seeding, as well as biocompatible properties were showed with pilot rabbit investigations [83,137]. On the other hand, different concentrations of Fe-HA material were tested in presence of Saos-2 human osteoblast-like cells in absence and in presence of external magnetic field, for 7 days. An improvement on cell activity in presence of static external magnetic field was observed, as well as, good biocompatibility was obtained after 4 weeks implanted into critical size lesion of rabbit condyle [137]. Osteogenic differentiation of human mesenchymal stem cells was obtained in presence of template composed of Fe-HA and PCL [140]. The magnetic performance was properly analysed, also showing a sigmoidal shape of the magnetization curve and a very low coercive field at 37 °C [140,141]. Furthermore, exciting insights about the combination design of time-dependent magnetic fields and magnetic nanocomposite structures to potentially guide cell behaviour was reported [142,143], as well as interesting results in terms of extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) 1/2 phosphorylation and, hence, in the activation of the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway was presented [143]. The obtained results are reported thanks to the close similarity of Fe-HA with mineral bone composition. Cytocompatibility, biocompatibility, osteoinductivity, osteoconductivity and bioactivity properties of Fe-HA, prompt their future use in biomedical applications as suitable tool for theragnostic, drug delivery, heat mediator for hyperthermia treatment, contrast agent for magnetic resonance imaging or as magnetic nanocarriers, and further can be suggested to substitute the commercial iron oxide nanoparticles [83,89,95,113,137,144,145].

4.2. Bio-inspired hybrid materials mineralised with Fe-HA

Bio-inspired biomineralisation process mimics the cascade phenomena occurring *in vivo* during new bone tissue formation. Heterogeneous nucleation of Fe-HA into collagen type I matrix [146–148], alginate [101,149] and RCP [99,100,122] were successful achieved.

This process activates several physicochemical and morphological mechanisms that constrain the inorganic phase to nucleate in specific *loci* of collagen macromolecule, and limit the crystal growth to few nanometres with very low crystal ordering and specific orientation, similarly as occurring in the newly formed bone [84,147]. The obtained hybrid construct exhibited high compositional and structural mimicry of bone tissue with excellent biocompatibility, osteogenic ability and

intrinsic superparamagnetic properties enabling remote activation by magnetic signalling [148].

The ability of natural polymers, such as collagen or RCP to expose negatively charged functional groups enabling the link of Ca^{2+} or Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} ions and subsequent heterogeneous nucleation of apatite nanophases [99,138].

For instance, alginate matrix (an algal polymer) was successfully

Fig. 3. Bio-inspired materials with superparamagnetic features. A) Sketch of bio-inspired biominerallization process. B) Morphological, chemical, and magnetic properties of the as-synthesised materials. C) Cell viability and expression of bone related genes. D) Superparamagnetic microspheres as a carrier of rhBMP-2. Adapted from [1,100,122,138].

mineralised with Fe-HA and then engineered into nanobeads. Superparamagnetic properties and cytocompatibility in presence of Mouse Fibroblasts (BALB/3T3 Clone A31) were presented and are suggested for various applications in nanomedicine and it is hypothesised that can replace the current used SPIONs [149]. Fe-HA phase was heterogeneously nucleated on RCP matrix obtaining a slurry that can be engineered into microspheres by an emulsification process [99,100] and was named as RCPFeHA (Fig. 3). RCPFeHA microspheres were functionalised with citrate ions and a biomimetic surface functionalization with improved bioactivity and with dispersion ability in cell culture medium was achieved [100]. Bone-like composition, superparamagnetic properties, good degradation rate, iron release, non-cytotoxic effect, osteogenic differentiation in presence of MC3T3-E1 cell line and human mesenchymal stem cells are also highlighted (Fig. 3A, 3B, 3C) [100,122,138]. The feasibility of RCPFeHA microspheres as a drug carrier was investigated with rhBMP-2. The magnetic mineralised phase allowed a markedly slower release profile, thanks to electrostatic interaction of carboxylic groups of rhBMP-2 with positively charged ions (e.g. Ca^{2+} , $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$) exposed on the apatite surface, as well as by the water bridge H-bonds between OH and NH_2 groups of the RCP protein and PO_4^{3-} charge on the apatite surface, compared with free-iron microspheres. Nevertheless, RCPFeHA are sensitive to external magnetic fields showing a slight increase on rhBMP-2 release in presence of low-frequency PEMFs (Fig. 3D) [122].

The finding suggests that effective activation of magneto-shaking mechanisms for magnetically controlled release of bioactive molecules can be favoured by establishing a chemical link between the magnetic phase and the molecule to be released. It is also shown that the release extent can be modulated by the application of PEMF, thus showing the potential of remote controlling the bioactivity of the new micro-devices which is promising for future application of hybrid biomimetic microspheres in precisely designed and personalized therapies. Bone-like and magnetic properties of the as-mentioned devices promotes their ability to be used in bone tissue regeneration and be activated by external magnetic field that can be promising on boost regeneration of extended bone or osteochondral regions [98,100,122,138,148,150].

5. Magnetic-based strategies for bone tissue regeneration

Aging, diseases, or immunodeficiency's can affect and reduce the physiological regenerative process and the endogenous regenerative potential of bone tissue. In the case of bone replacement needed, a variety of substitutes are currently available in the market. Moreover, they do not meet relevant aspects related to the induction of cell differentiation, angiogenesis process, osteoinduction and osteoconduction [151]. Researchers have found that bone substitutes combined with growth factors, microRNAs or drugs can be benefit on recruiting endogenous cells, although their reduced bioactivity and non-controlled release over the time can limit their application [124]. Therefore, special attention to bioactive magnetic materials elicits ever-growing interest, as therapeutic agents. They have potential on boosting bone regeneration process, by *on-demand* release of bioactive factors. On the other hand, combining magnetic materials with magnetic stimulation can be used as cancer therapy to remove the cancer cells and simultaneously to promote tissue regeneration.

5.1. Magnetic scaffolds and magnetic stimulation

Magnetite and maghemite are the most common superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs, size range from 10 nm to 3.5 μm) investigated for biomedical applications [150,152]. The greatest advantage of using those materials are they capability to present high magnetization in presence of an external magnetic field and any magnetization is maintain upon removal of the field, as well as good biocompatibility, low toxicity, biodegradability and chemical stability in the presence of the cells prompt their use in bone regeneration process

and bone tissue engineering, as well as in cancer therapy [150,152–155].

Scaffolds with magnetic properties can be obtained by (i) the incorporation of magnetic nanoparticles into ceramic [132,137,156], composite [157–160], polymer [161–165], or in presence of natural based materials, as chitosan [166], bombyx mori silk fibroin [167,168] and collagen [169]; or by (ii) the immersion in ferrofluids [169].

Various studies have been carried out and indicate that magnetic phase improves scaffold stiffness, crosstalk between integrin-mediated signals from cells and soluble factors, cell adhesion, proliferation, and osteogenic activity *in vitro* and bone formation *in vivo* (Table 3).

Regarding to bone tissue engineering, the magnetic properties can influence the osteogenesis process by increasing the permeability of the cell membrane, which consequently influences the passage of ions, naturally increasing cell activity [172,173]. On the other hand, the improvement of cell permeability in the membrane can be associated with the phospholipids present in it and with the increase in conductivity due to the enormous passage of ions, producing electrical bio-effects that promote bone remodelling [172]. Additionally, calcium ions are extremely important for different cellular functions, so the protein kinase activity could be influenced by magnetic fields, changing the concentration of ions that participate in the regulation of other proteins, such as cyclin, which is highly involved with the regulation of osteoblasts (Fig. 4) [172,173]. Finally, magnetic activity may be associated with the activation of the adenosine monophosphate system, activating several enzymatic cascades, inducing functions in the cells responsible for bone remodelling, and consequently may be associated with bone growth [172].

Bone regeneration process can be governed by switching the magnetization input provided by superparamagnetic features of bio-materials and activated by an external magnetic field (EMF), promoting an interaction between cells and scaffold, which might influence mechano-transduction pathway (i.e. cells translate physical stimuli into biochemical activity) [150,174,175]. It can enhance cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation, promote osteogenesis, angiogenesis, regulate the inflammatory process, as well as improves bone formation *in vivo* (Table 4). Nevertheless, M. Marcacci and co-authors showed that *in vivo* magnetic fixation of HAP/collagen magnetic scaffolds and their possibility on controlling the tissue regeneration [156,176]. The effect of magnetic materials with magnetic field open a revolutionary approach in medicine by *on demand* boosting tissue regeneration [84,89,150].

In the case of cancer therapy, magnetic scaffolds have been investigated as potential instruments for the treatment of bone malignancies, to limit recurrence, and in boosting radiotherapy and chemotherapy effectiveness. An external magnetic field can be used to manipulate the microenvironment, support osteoblast differentiation and proliferation, promote the expression of certain growth factors, and ultimately speed up the production of new bone [187]. The scaffold architecture can be modified to include stimulus-responsive nanocarriers, such as magnetic nanoparticles functionalized with bioactive chemicals, whose behaviour can be precisely regulated by external magnetic conduction and which promote the growth of bone tissue [187].

5.2. Tissue response

The inflammatory response is the first stage associated to the bone healing (non-infectious damage-associated molecular patterns, DAMPs) or can be related with the presence of bacteria or pathogens into the damaged tissue (infectious pathogen-associated molecular patterns, PAMPs). DAMPs are endogenous molecules that are expressed by the injured tissue (e.g. heat shock proteins, high-mobility group box 1 (HMGB1), inflammatory cytokines (IL-1 α) and fragments of ECM), which stimulates the immune system. DAMPs and PAMPs activate the immune system to defend the body against inflammation and several pattern recognition receptors (e.g. toll-like receptors, receptors for the

Table 3

Examples of as-investigated magnetic scaffolds for bone tissue engineering. (BG: bioactive glass; BSA: bovine serum albumin; CA: citric acid; CaP: calcium phosphate; CS: chitosan; DXM: corticosteroid dexamethasone acetate; HA: hydroxyapatite; hBMSC: human bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells; MSCs: mesenchymal stem cells; MNPs: magnetic nanoparticles; MGB: polymer P123 and polyurethane sponges; PLA: poly lactic acid; PLGA: poly(d,l-lactide-co-glycolide); rBMSCs: Rat bone marrow stromal cells; SBF: simulated body fluid; SMF: static magnetic field; SPIONS: Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles.).

Material	Template	Study	Cells/ Animal model	Saturation Magnetization (emu/g)	Biological effect / advantages	Ref.
Mesoporous silica coated magnetic (Fe ₃ O ₄)	Nanoparticles	<i>In vitro</i> / <i>in vivo</i>	MSCs / adult male Sprague–Dawley rats	Data not showed	Good biocompatibility; Promotes osteogenic differentiation of MSCs; Accelerate bone regeneration in rat model.	[160]
CaP coated γ -Fe ₂ O ₃ – BSA	Nanoparticles	<i>In vitro</i>	Human osteoblasts	3.47 – 33.58	CaP coated γ -Fe ₂ O ₃ – BSA: high osteoblasts density.	[132]
CaP coated γ -Fe ₂ O ₃ – CA	Nanoparticles	<i>In vitro</i>	Human osteoblasts	65—67	Cytocompatibility and increase osteogenesis-related gene expression (RUNX2, BGLAP and SPP1).	[159]
Poly(lactic acid) loaded with hydroxyapatite and iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs) and an antibiotic (minocycline)	Scaffolds	<i>In vitro</i>	Human osteosarcoma cell line MG-63	65—67	Cytocompatibility and increase osteogenesis-related gene expression (RUNX2, BGLAP and SPP1).	[159]
HAp/collagen (70:30 w/w) immersed in commercial ferrofluids	Scaffolds	<i>In vitro</i>	hBMSC	13–15	Scaffolds were able to support cell adhesion and proliferation <i>in vitro</i> .	[169]
Fe5% –MGB and Fe10%–MGB	Scaffolds calcined at 700 °C	<i>In vitro</i>	hBMSC	5 % \approx 1 10 % \approx 0.2	MNPs: Enhances the mitochondrial activity gene expression; Magnetic properties can be enhanced by iron amount; Sustained drug release.	[164]
Bioactive glasses with MNPs and SBF biomineralisation	Scaffolds produced by Salt-leaching techniques (calcined during different timings)	<i>In vitro</i>	HeLa cells	50': 6.78 70': 3.72 90': 3.19 110': 1.96	Good biocompatibility and cell adherence ability.	[158]
Polycaprolactone/ MNPs	Electrospun nanofibers	<i>In vitro</i> / <i>In vivo</i>	Osteoblasts / Male Sprague-Dawley Rats	1.0—11.2	<i>In vitro</i> : improve cell adhesion; <i>In vivo</i> : Significant bone formation.	[165]
Calcium phosphate cement containing maghemite and hematite nanoparticles	Bone cement	<i>In vitro</i>	Human dental pulp stem cells	\approx 0.5	Improvement on cell adhesion, spreading and substantial osteogenic differentiation.	[170]
Self-setting calcium phosphate cements with incorporated magnetic nanoparticles	Bone cement	<i>In vitro</i>	rBMSCs	0.05: (0.1 % MNP) 0.35: (1 % MNP)	Altered the crystal configuration of hydroxyapatite from large to small needle-like crystals, improves the mechanical strength, cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation, making those materials an interesting tool for bone tissue repair.	[171]

Fig. 4. Magnetic effect on bone tissue regeneration.

Table 4
Magnetic scaffolds and magnetic stimulation for bone tissue engineering.

Material	Template	Study	Cells/ Animal model	Magnetic field: Type and intensity	Saturation Magnetization (emu/g)	Biological effect / advantages	Ref.
Silk fibroin/chitosan-based magnetic scaffolds	MNPs (reverse co-precipitation method) in scaffolds	<i>In vitro</i>	MG-63 Osteosarcoma cells	Constant magnetic field	Data not showed	MNPs with superparamagnetic behaviour; Good cellular behaviour.	[168]
Polyglycolic acid as matrix and Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles	Scaffold	<i>In vitro</i> and <i>In vivo</i>	Human umbilical cord-derived mesenchymal stem cells and rabbit radius defect.	<i>In vitro</i> , SMF permanent magnet. <i>In vivo</i> , magnetic field intensity: 40–70 mT for the sides of the cages, and 1.2–5.6 mT for the middle area.	Max 6.78	<i>In vitro</i> , scaffold exhibited significantly enhanced gene expression of alkaline phosphatase, osteocalcin, type I collagen and runt-related transcription factor-2. <i>In vivo</i> , the bone regeneration was improved.	[177]
IP-L780 photopolymer coated with layer of collagen-chitosan-hydroxyapatite-magnetic nanoparticles	Scaffold	<i>In vitro</i>	MG-63 osteoblast-like cells	SMF (100–250 mT)	n.a.	SMF: accelerates the cell differentiation <i>in vitro</i> ; Intense magnetic field induces cell proliferation and differentiation.	[178]
Super-paramagnetic c-Fe ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles (MNP), hydroxyapatite nanoparticles (nHA) and poly lactide acid (PLA)	Scaffold	<i>In vivo</i>	White rabbit model, of lumbar transverse defects	SMF (0.05–0.2 mT for the middle plane of the cage) / (5–25 mT for the two sides)	0.049	SMF accelerates new bone tissue formation and remodelling in the rabbit defect.	[179]
Polycaprolactone/magnetic nanoparticles	Scaffold	<i>In vitro</i> / <i>In vivo</i>	Primary mouse calvarium osteoblasts; Female 6- to 8-week-old ICR mice	SMF (15mT) <i>In vivo</i> (mT (15–25 mT at sides and 0.05–0.2 mT at central region)	≈ 1.7 – 4.8	SMF promoted the angiogenic responses of endothelial cells, including the expression of vascular endothelial growth factor and angiogenin ¹ genes and the formation of capillary tubes; SMF significantly enhanced the new bone formation after 6 weeks in mouse calvarium defects.	[163]
PLLA/Fe ₃ O ₄ composite	Nanofibers	<i>In vitro</i>	MC3T3-E1 osteoblasts	SMF (1 mT–1 T)	≈ 1.94–3.51	Magnetic feature regulates the osteogenesis.	[180]
Tri-block copolymer poly (ε-caprolactone)-poly (ethylene glycol)-poly (ε-caprolactone) (PCL-PEG-PCL, PCEC) and magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (Fe ₃ O ₄ NPs)	Nanofibers (electrospinning)	<i>In vitro</i>	NIH 3 T3 cells	n.a.	n.a.	Suitable scaffold for cell adhesion.	[173]
Magnetic g-Fe ₂ O ₃ nanoparticles coated with meso-2, 3-dimercaptosuccinic acid	Magnetic nanofibrous scaffolds	<i>In vitro</i> / <i>In vivo</i>	Murine monocyte macrophage cell line (RAW264.7) and preosteoblast cell (MC3T3-E1); Six-weekold male C57	SMF (0–40 mT; interval of 12 h up to 72 h)	<2.2	Inhibition of secretion of the pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1b, TNF-a and MCP-1 and osteoclast differentiation cytokines MMP-9 and TRAP; Upregulation of VEGF and PDGF.	[181]
SPIOs with DXM co-encapsulate in PLGA	Microspheres (1—10 μm)	<i>In vitro</i>	Human synovial fibroblasts	SMF (0.6 – 1 T)	Data not showed	Excellent biocompatibility; Particles internalized through phagocytic process; Do not induce any inflammatory reaction.	[182]
HA/collagen (70/30 wt%) with nucleated 4 wt% MNPs and HA/collagen (70/30 wt%) immersed in ferrofluid	Scaffolds	<i>In vivo</i>	Male rabbits	Magnetic field 1.2 T	Data not showed	Magnetic forces influence the orientation of scaffold architecture; Higher bone healing rate in scaffold nucleated with MNPs, without inflammatory reaction.	[156]
MNPs (2, 1 & 0.5 %) in discs of HA	Porous discs immersed in colloid solution of MNPs	<i>In vitro</i>	ROS 17/2.8 MC3T3-E1	Magnetic field with Helmholtz coil; Intensity 10 Oe, Frequency 50 Hz	2 % – 0.94 1 % – 0.53 0.5 % – 0.24	MNPs: Stimulate cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation; MNPs with SMF: enhances cell proliferation and differentiation.	[183]
Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (MNP) incorporated in calcium phosphate	Cement	<i>In vitro</i> / <i>In vivo</i>	Human dental pulp stem cells; Male Sprague Dawley rats	SMF (35 ± 5 mT)	≈ 0.6	MNP incorporation: improve biocompatibility and enhance the osteoinduction of stem cells on CPC; SMF and MNPs accelerate the	[184]

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Material	Template	Study	Cells/ Animal model	Magnetic field: Type and intensity	Saturation Magnetization (emu/g)	Biological effect / advantages	Ref.
Calcium sulphate hemihydrate composites reinforced with BiFeO ₃ (multiferroic material)	Cement	<i>In vitro</i>	MC3T3 cells	Magnetic field, 200 mT	0.1 – 0.01	biological behaviours of the cells, resulting in new bone regeneration <i>in vivo</i> . High osteoblasts cell viability, differentiation and mineralization in presence of magnetic and electrical stimuli.	[185]
Oleic acid modified iron oxide nanoparticles (IO-OA NPs) and poly(lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA)	Scaffold	<i>In vitro</i>	MC3T3 cells	70–80 mT	IO-OA NP content (0.5 % w/w): 0.24; IO-OA NP content (1 % w/w): 0.43; IO-OA NP content (5 % w/w): 2.07;	Cell attachment and osteogenic differentiation; Improved alkaline phosphatase activity, increase on mineralized nodule formation, and upregulated bone-associated gene expression (ALP, OCN, and BMP2), in a dose- and time-dependent manner by applying an external magnetic field.	[186]

advanced glycation end products) are enrolled and are presented on the antigen presenting cells (i.e. dendritic cells and macrophages). The receptors influence a response by the activation of transcriptional factors (i.e. nuclear factor kappa-light-chain enhancer of activated B cells (NF- κ B) or interferon regulatory factors) [188].

The properties of healthy bone tissue are crucial for the function of the desired scaffolds after implantation. Scaffolds properties are also relevant in the modulation of the immune response with the regard to reduce the inflammatory process and to be recognised as an endogenous material that can facilitate the regenerative cascade. Monocytes are differentiated into macrophages and then they attached to the scaffold. Osteoblasts result from mesenchymal progenitor (MPs) via pre-osteoblasts and control the mineralisation of extracellular collagen protein matrix (ECM). The subset of osteoblasts become osteocytes, mature bone cells embedded into the bone matrix, which are thought to control and direct the physiological bone turnover based on continuous formation and resorption of bone tissue, in response to damaging or to mechanical stimuli (bone remodelling). In the early stage of new bone formation, osteoblasts attachment, proliferation and differentiation are key phenomena for bone formation, by the production of matrix proteins, such as collagen type I, osteopontin, bone sialoprotein, osteonectin, osteocalcin, fibronectin and bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs) prior to mineral deposition [189]. Osteoclasts are multinucleated resorptive cells derived from bone marrow-derived macrophages, which are in turn progenies of haematopoietic stem cells (HSCs). Osteoclasts remove bone mineral and bone matrix in a process named as bone resorption, therefore bone-lining cells prevents osteoclasts interaction with bone matrix in dysfunctional situation, as well as it seems to be relevant in coupling bone resorption to bone formation [61,65,190–192].

The inflammatory response after scaffold implantation can be reduced with the use of antibiotics. However, the potential risk of antibiotic resistance or reduced effectiveness is the biggest concerns on limiting the inflammatory process after bone substitute implantation. On the other hand, the use of high doses of antibiotics can negatively affect osteogenesis, as well as the regenerative cascade [193].

Immune cells (e.g. neutrophils, mast cells, dendritic cells, T cells, monocytes and macrophages) are actively enrolled in bone physiology and pathology [194]. In the damaged tissue, neutrophils are the first activated cells for the removal of contaminants, through secretion of various antimicrobial substances and proteases. Therefore, neutrophils secrete several cytokines and growth factors, which can emulate the migration of more neutrophils and other immune cells (i.e. macrophages) to the damage local. Macrophages also plays a relevant role on tissue remodelling by secreting several cytokines, recruiting cells to

damaged tissue, as well as are responsible for phagocytosis of undesired material. The high polarization of macrophages can modify their functional phenotype and can be easily adapted to the placed microenvironment. M1 and M2 are two typical polarized macrophages related with pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory phenotypes, respectively. M1 are enrolled in the phagocytosis of dead cells and pathogens, as well as they produce various pro-inflammatory cytokines. The activity of M1 phenotype is about 3–4 days after damage and then they change to M2 phenotype [124,188].

Physical stimuli (i.e. mechanical, electrical and / or magnetic) can enable an improved tissue regeneration [195]. It is possible due to the pyroelectric, ferroelectric, and piezoelectric properties of natural living bones [175]. In fact, bone and cartilage cells actively react to mechanical stress, fluid flow, pH, and pO₂ by modifying their phenotype and by expression of a variety of signals, translated in the modification of extracellular matrix organization, boost the proliferation and differentiation of osteoblasts-like primary cells, bone mineralization and angiogenesis [76,196–200].

Electrical stimulation showed beneficial effects during the treatment of bone, mainly in the anti-inflammatory, chondrogenesis, osteogenesis and vascularization processes. The positive effects were observed in terms of an upregulation of osteogenic genes transcription in macrophages, stimulation of Ca pathways, upregulation of bone morphogenetic proteins, growth factors, cytokines, cells differentiation and mineralization [7,175].

From another perspective, magnetic field plays a key role on cellular behaviour and, several studies regarding the application of magnetic fields on cells highlights that this external stimulus benefits cell physiological activities, such as proliferation, osteogenic differentiation, secretion of growth factors, and angiogenesis [201,202]. Nonetheless, these physiological changes are largely determined by magnetic field physical properties such as waveform and frequency, whereas the applied magnetic field dose is determined by field strength and exposure duration [201]. Magnetic responsive materials, on the other hand, require an external magnetic source, which is typically a static magnetic or pulsed electromagnetic field. According to the intensity of the signal, static magnetic field intensity is divided into several categories. It has been reported that, aside from the ultra-weak (5 T-1 mT) and weak magnetic field (1 mT), an intensity range between 1 mT and 5 T can in fact promote cellular proliferation and osteogenic differentiation [203]. The use of magnetic scaffolds combined with the application of a magnetic field has been shown to increase the expression of osteogenic markers such as alkaline phosphatase (ALP), activate vascular differentiation of endothelial cells, polarize adipose-derived stem cells, and promote intercellular interactions, thereby enhancing the formation of

mineralized nodules [163,204], and substantially accelerated bone regeneration [177]. However, prolonged and continuous exposure to these physical stimuli can have a negative impact on osteogenesis by inhibiting this process via cytokine secretion and adipose-derived stem cell proliferation [205].

Exposure to low frequencies of a pulsed electromagnetic field (low-frequency PEMF), on the other hand, has a positive impact on cell proliferation, differentiation, and the regulation of the cytokine cell cycle. Furthermore, low-frequency PEMF regulates inflammatory responses during osteogenesis by increasing anti-inflammatory factor expression, decreasing inflammatory responses, and promoting the formation of new bone tissue [206]. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved the use of pulsed electromagnetic fields (PEMFs) for the healing of non-union bone, in non-invasive, cost-effective, and safe way. PEMF improves the synthesis of cartilage and bone matrix growth factors, as well as enhance the proliferation and differentiation of osteoblast-like primary cells [196]. PEMF generates an electromotive force that influences signal transmission, resulting in the activation of the focal adhesion kinase pathway and the migration of mesenchymal stem cells, thereby promoting bone tissue regeneration [198,206–208]. However, high frequencies of these stimuli can be harmful, causing genetic damage and inhibiting cell proliferation [209]. In overall, from a tissue engineering standpoint, manipulating the magnetic field will cause specific changes in the scaffold structure [210,211], which will be somewhat evasive and locally effective, allowing for controlled therapeutic action [212,213]. Nonetheless, even in the absence of a magnetic external stimulus, the incorporation of magnetic nanoparticles in scaffolds has been shown to be beneficial for bone tissue repair by improving osteogenesis [214,215].

For instance, a group of researchers manufactured a magnetic scaffold using selective laser sintering and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in poly-(L)-lactide/ polyglycolic acid (PLLA/PGA). As a result, each nanoparticle created a magnetic environment in which it was possible to promote cellular responses such as cell adhesion, viability, and proliferation rate even in the absence of external magnetic stimulation. The magnetic scaffolds were also found to promote osteogenesis and osteogenic differentiation in rabbits when tested *in vivo* [172]. Nevertheless, the authors also investigated the reinforcement of PLLA scaffolds with Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and graphene oxide (GO) nanosheets resulting on improved MG63 cells activity, proliferation and differentiation [216].

Despite this, some researchers have previously reported that the effect of magnetic particles under a magnetic field result in improved bone tissue repair [168,184,217]. Magnetic scaffolds can regulate osteogenic differentiation due to their mechanical properties and through the regulation of the magnetic field. For example, when the magnetic scaffold has a high stiffness (37.70 ± 19.60 kPa), it has a better osteogenic ability [218]. However, the application of a magnetic field will increase the stiffness of the magnetic scaffold due to the directional arrangement of magnetic particles inside the scaffold. Integrin-mediated activation of FAK or ERK1/2 phosphoric acid by a stiff matrix allows stem cells to differentiate into osteoblasts [219]. Concurrently, the PI3K/Akt pathway is activated, increasing the number of mitochondria, and causing morphological changes in cells to regulate osteogenic differentiation [220]. Furthermore, a stiff matrix can regulate the ERK pathway via integrin and activate transcriptional coactivator with PDZ-binding motif to increase the expression of osteogenic genes [221]. The tissue can activate an inflammatory response, if magnetic particles are leached into the extracellular matrix and cross the biological membrane. This can happen if the magnetic particles are smaller than 50 nm. As a result, it will induce oxidative stress, and reactive oxygen species will be released, leading to cell apoptosis [222]. Hence, to achieve a controlled and successful therapeutic action and to predict how magnetic particles will react to their incorporation into the polymeric network, proper models that consider the magnetic field strength, the amount of magnetic nanoparticles used, and the responsiveness of these magnetic particles to the applied magnetic field are still required [223].

5.3. Immune-modulated osteogenesis

One paradigm of tissue engineering is associated with the immune response and the influence of immunomodulators on the healing and regeneration of bone tissue. Despite advances in regenerative medicine and tissue engineering in recent years, the use of biomaterials in the human organism is recognized as a strange, disrupting immune system response [224].

The immune system is in charge of the body's defense, actively participating in the process of healing and bone regeneration through its lines of defense identified as innate and adaptive immunity [225] (Fig. 5). Innate immunity is the first line of defense, associating with a lack of specificity against microorganisms or other foreign components, and functions primarily in fighting infection, removing waste products from fighting infection, and regenerating damaged tissue through the release of growth factors [226,227].

Macrophages consist of cells of the innate immune system with characteristics of polarization and plasticity, allowing macrophages to differentiate according to their polarity in M1 and M2 depending on the inducing agents, the function and the markers present on their surface [228]. The M1 macrophage, consists of the subtype of macrophages, triggered by the presence of interferon- γ and lipopolysaccharides, with properties of secretion of pro-inflammatory mediators, anti-infectious properties and involvement in the anti-tumor process [228–230]. Additionally, when regulated activation of M1 occurs, they play important roles in the osteogenic process, namely in the differentiation of mesenchymal stromal cells through the mediation of bone morphogenetic protein 2 (BMP2) [228]. On the other hand, M2 macrophages are a subtype of macrophages triggered by the presence of IL-4, IL-10 and IL-13 that differentiate into M2a, M2b and M2c, depending on their functions [228,230]. These essentially participate in anti-inflammatory activity, promoting repair of bone tissue, angiogenesis, immunosuppression, and tumor progression [228,230].

The innate immune system has other important cell types for the body's defense mechanism, such as neutrophils. These actively participate in the immune regulation of bone tissue, presenting pro-inflammatory functions in the initial stages of the inflammatory process and anti-inflammatory functions after the inflammatory process, their function being determined by polarity, similar to macrophages (Fig. 5) [228,231]. The polarization of neutrophils in N1 or N2 is dependent on the levels of inflammatory mediators, namely IL-8 [228,232]. In the case of N1 neutrophils, the increase of IL-8 will polarize the neutrophil towards performing pro-inflammatory functions, namely in the recruitment of M1 macrophages, TH1 and TH17 to the sites of tissue injury [228,232]. On the other hand, N2 neutrophils arise from the polarization process when IL-8 levels decrease, allowing the acquisition of anti-inflammatory characteristics, participating in the bone remodeling process [228,232]. Additionally, N2 neutrophils participates in the recruitment of bone marrow stromal cells (BMSCs), through the release of SDF-1 α which acts through the activation of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway, with consequent migration mediated by β - catenin, and this step is important to enhance bone tissue regeneration [228,232,233].

Adaptive immunity, contrary to innate immunity (Fig. 5), consists of the action of specialized cells against a specific agent, constituting the most sophisticated line of defense of the immune system. The cells that develop adaptive immunity are essentially T lymphocytes and B lymphocytes [228].

T lymphocytes differentiate into TH1, TH2, TH17 and Treg subtypes, which are responsible for the production and secretion of inflammatory mediators and macrophage activation, suppression of macrophage function, inflammation and tissue damage, and the suppression of osteoclast differentiation, respectively [228]. On the other hand, B lymphocytes actively participate in the regulation of bone formation and in the metabolic process, regulating the process from the release of several immunological mediators, such as the cytokines TNF- α , TNF- β ,

Fig. 5. The role of the immune system in bone tissue healing and regeneration, a) innate immunity and b) adaptive immunity, . Adapted from: [225–228,230,232]

IL-6, IL-10 and CCL3 chemokines [228]. Additionally, B and T cells participate in the regulation of RANKL/RANK/OPG signaling pathways, which are pathways associated with osteoclast maturation and bone remodeling [228,234].

The complexity of the immune system response and the active participation in the mechanism of bone regeneration, for the development and application of biomaterials, the obstacles of the inflammatory process and the immune response must be considered. The presence of damage in bone tissue is associated with an inflammatory process, so the implanted structures must act to minimize the possibility of an exacerbated reaction on the part of the immune system and act to enhance the immune response to the healing process and bone regeneration [235].

Currently, biomaterials have been studied for their ability to induce regulation in the process of healing, repair, and regeneration of bone tissue through the immune system [228]. Thus, the success and assimilation of biomaterials will be determined by the interaction of biomaterials with immunomodulatory properties with the immunological microenvironment [224,236]. In this sense, evolution has followed the direction of developing biomaterials with immunomodulating

properties, inducing the process of healing, repair, and regeneration of bone tissue, with the aim of circumventing some of the associated problems, thus allowing a better integration with the organism and contributing to better healing of bone tissue [224,237,238].

A recent study conducted by Shanbhag and collaborators aimed to evaluate the influence of dicalcium phosphates (BCP) on mesenchymal stromal cell (MSC) responses and MSC interactions with macrophages, regarding the expression of genes and proteins exposed to the inflammatory microenvironment [239]. The results showed an increase in the expression of BMP2, VEGF, and IL-10 genes that are associated with osteogenesis and the bone healing process, as well as the repression of genes associated with inflammation [239]. This study concluded that in the presence or absence of an inflammatory environment, in the presence or absence of macrophages, BCP regulates the expression of genes related to osteogenesis, healing and inflammation, promoting a phenotype towards pro-healing, being these findings consistent for the two types of scaffolds used [239].

On the other hand, creating biomaterials that reduce a host's negative immune response is one of the hurdles in tissue engineering [240].

Fig. 5. (continued).

As a result, modern biomaterials in development are employed to modify the immune response, promoting the immune response to support the healing of bone tissue. After implantation, there are two successive processes in the regeneration process. Monocytes first move to the area of inflammation, then differentiate into macrophages and begin to degrade the scaffold as a result of their activities [240]. On the other side, the release of cytokines induces a healing process that is anti-inflammatory [240]. Modulating the characteristics of scaffolds without sacrificing their usefulness is necessary to maintain the balance between tissue regeneration and scaffold breakdown, which is crucial [240]. Important elements including biomaterial qualities, surface chemistry, topography, form, degradability, and mechanical properties might affect how the immune system reacts to a scaffold. In order to achieve the best immune response, it is essential to balance the qualities in this way [240]. The scaffold has the potential to improve cell adhesion, metabolic activity, differentiation, and modulation of the synthesis of bioactive chemicals, enabling control of the organism's innate immunity [240].

The benefits of using magnetic scaffolds are understood, and their potential significance in stimulating bone tissue growth is now being explored [192].

In this context, magnetic lanthanum-doped hydroxyapatite/ chitosan scaffolds (MLaHA/CS) showed promising properties on recruiting rat bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (rBMSCs) and modulating host-to-scaffold immune responses by promoting macrophage polarization into the anti-inflammatory phenotype (M2) *in vitro*, when compared to hydroxyapatite/ chitosan scaffolds (HA/CS) and lanthanum-doped hydroxyapatite/ chitosan scaffolds (LaHA/CS). An improved formation of collagen fibers and osteogenic properties, as well as M2 polarization were respectively observed by Van Gieson and CD206 staining for magnetic scaffolds. Moreover, an osteogenic differentiation *in vitro* and bone formation in rat calvarial defects were obtained [124] (Fig. 6A). Wu and co-authors developed an *in vivo* model composed of protein corona and magnetic hydroxyapatite scaffolds (MHA) to evaluate the inflammatory reaction and bone wound healing. The results indicated that the magnetic phase inhibited the chronic inflammatory response and enhance the acute inflammatory response, through the recruitment of immune cells, remodelling of extracellular matrix and improving of bone healing [241] (Fig. 6B).

Fig. 6. A) Van Gieson staining (a) and CD206 immunohistochemical staining of craniums with three cranial defects implanted with HA/CS, LaHA/CS, and MLaHA/CS scaffolds (b); B) Schematic representation of the immune-modulating osteogenesis of the MHA scaffold through dynamic protein corona. Adapted from [124,241].

5.4. Bone tumour ablation and tissue regeneration

Bone tumors are one of the concerns in the search for therapeutic solutions given the associated malignancy, mortality rate and morbidities for patients [242]. Generally, primary tumors derive from primitive mesenchymal cells, constituting sarcomas presenting an incidence of 0.2 % of bone malignant tumors [243]. Secondary bone tumors, on the other hand, are frequently caused by the metastasis of breast, lung, and prostate tumors, with bone being the third most common site of

metastasis, affecting 65–75 % of patients with advanced metastatic progression [244]. Currently, the conventional therapeutic strategies implemented are surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy; however, the complexity of these tumors frequently makes surgical removal incomplete, increase the probability of relapse and metastasis. Furthermore, chemotherapy and radiotherapy have numerous negative consequences, and some bone tumors, such as osteosarcoma, are resistant to these therapeutic interventions in many cases [245].

Considering the complexity and malignancy of bone tumors, as well

NANOPARTICLES	TRANSPORTER	CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC DRUG
 POLYMERIC NANOPARTICLES	Coupling of Methotrexate with PGA nanoparticles Keratin nanoparticles functionalized by Chlorin-e6 PLGA nanoparticles Poly (ESTER AMIDE) Poloxamers modified with trimethyl chitosan	Methotrexate Paclitaxel Salinomycin Apatinib Methotrexate
 POLYMERIC MICELLES	HA - octadecanoic acid (contains alendronate) Bone - targeting micelles Micelles with RGD- modified PEG - block- poly (trimethylene carbonate) copolymer	Curcumin Doxorubicin
 LIPOSOMES	COS modified liposomes PEGylated liposomes PEGylated liposomes coated with gold nanoshells Liposomes modified with alendronic acid and LMWH	Doxorubicin Gemcitabine Clofazimine Betulinic acid Doxorubicin
 MESOPOROUS SILICA NANOPARTICLES	PEI- modified and iron oxide - loaded mesoporous silica nanoparticles	Doxorubicin
 CARBON NANOMATERIALS	(TRA/GO nano-complexes)	Trastuzumab
 CALCIUM PHOSPHATES NANOPARTICLES	Bisphosphonate modified HANPs	JQ1
 METALLIC NANOPARTICLES	Fe3O4 - based nanoparticles	Gemcitabine
 POLYMERIC NANOGELS	HA - based nanogels	Cisplatin Doxorubicin

Fig. 7. Main strategies for the application of biomaterials in the transport of chemotherapy for bone tumors, specifically for osteosarcoma. (PGA: poly glycerol adipate; PLGA: poly lactic-co-glycolic acid; HA: hyaluronic acid; RGD: arginine-glycine-aspartic peptide acid; PEI: Polyethyleneimine; HANPs: hydroxyapatite nanoparticles; TRA: Trastuzumab; GO: graphene oxide; JQ1: small-molecule bromodomain inhibitor; COS: chito oligosaccharides; PEG: polyethylene glycol; LMWH: low molecular weight heparin). Adapted from [207,248–262]

as the mortality rate and disadvantages of conventional therapeutic strategies, new therapeutic approaches for the treatment of bone tumors were required [246]. Thereby, studies for the application of biomaterials in the treatment of bone tumors and for the healing and regeneration of bone tissue have emerged over the years, introducing biomaterials as a new therapeutic strategy for bone tumors [233].

The history of the application of biomaterials for the repair of bone tissue is described from the beginning of the 20th century, through an American surgeon, through the attempt to implant calcium phosphates [56,184]. Currently, the development of strategies for application in bone has been concentrated in a bidirectional way, addressing the treatment of oncological disease and regeneration of the bone tissue itself [242]. Thus, the biomaterials currently under development favor the ideal environment and support for the development, growth, and cell proliferation for the healing of bone tissue, as well as the inclusion of the anti-tumor therapeutic effect and the favoring of bone regeneration. One of the current strategies is the transport of chemotherapeutic drugs encapsulated in nanoparticles [184]. A variety of nanoparticles (e.g. polymeric, polymeric micelles, liposomes, mesoporous silica, carbon, calcium phosphates, metallic or polymeric nanogels) has been investigated as a carrier of chemotherapeutic drugs in osteosarcoma (Fig. 7). These systems allow substances to remain in the organism for extended periods of time, directing treatment to the target area and, as a result, improving therapeutic competence for the treatment of bone tumor [184]. This therapeutic approach may also allow a reduction in systemic

toxicity, often associated with conventional chemotherapy [205,247].

On demand release of drugs or growth factors from magnetic carriers can be tailored by applying external magnetic fields. Moreover, cells behavior can be affected by the exposition of singular magnetic nanoparticle and micromotions at the interface between cells and the scaffold might affect the ion channels in the cell membrane and trigger the mechanotransduction pathway [150].

Magnetic hyperthermia is an anticancer treatment approach based on implantation of magnetic structures combined with an external magnetic field. The application of the external magnetic field generates temperature (40 °C–46 °C) that changes the physiology of malignant cells leading to apoptosis, whereas temperatures higher than 46 °C promote necrosis [263], without negative effect on the surrounding healthy cells [61,264,265]. In addition, this technique increases sensitivity for the application of other therapeutic strategies, such as chemotherapy [266]. The heating mechanism in superparamagnetic particles can be explained by Brownian and Néel relaxation. Brownian relaxation (i.e. heat effect stimulated by friction arising from total particle oscillations inside of medium (external dynamics)) and Néel relaxation (i.e. heat is mediated by the rotation of the magnetic moment with each field oscillation relative to crystal lattice (internal dynamics)) [128,267]. Zhou and co-authors tested magnetic calcium phosphate nanoparticles, as carriers of doxorubicin hydrochloride and DNA, and suitable properties for cancer therapy were obtained. By applying an external magnetic field an inhibition of tumour growth was observed, as

Fig. 8. A) Effect of bone cement therapy *in vivo*: magneto thermal curves and thermal image (a, c); Relative tumour volume variation (b) and photographs of tumours at day 14 (d); hematoxylin and eosin staining images of the tumour tissue and lung tissue (e). B) IR thermal images (a) and heating curves (b) of tumour-bearing mice post-implanted with BG and BG-5CFS scaffolds under the 808-nm laser irradiation taken at different time interval; The representative photographs (c) of nude mice after different treatments at day 0 (left) and day 14 (right); (d) Photographs of tumours obtained from four groups at day 14; (e) Relative tumour volume variation curve in four groups with increasing days ($n = 4$); (f) The whole-body fluorescence images (c) of nude mice at day 0 (up) and day 14 (down). The hyperthermia given off by photothermal effect of BG-5CFS scaffolds could effectively suppress tumour growth *in vivo*. Adapted from [157,269].

well as high transfection efficiency in A549 (adenocarcinomic human alveolar basal epithelial cells) and HepG2 (human liver carcinoma cell line) cells, was showed [268].

Magnetic bone cement was synthesized with different amounts of magnetic and graphite-nanostructured composite into α -tricalcium phosphate (α -TCP)/calcium sulfate (CS) biphasic bone cement. It showed magnetothermal property, that can reduce the tumour cells and metastasis, as well as to promote bone tissue regeneration [269] (Fig. 8A). Magnetic SrFe₁₂O₁₉ nanoparticles modified-mesoporous bio-glass (BG)/chitosan (CS) porous scaffold (MBCS) enhanced the expression levels of osteogenic-related genes and bone regeneration. On the other hand, the *in vivo* tests indicated that tumour was reduced by the exposure to near-infrared (NIR) laser [166]. Recently, Zhao and his collaborators [187] developed a cement with superparamagnetic properties, injectable Mn-Zn-Cu-Gd coated with SiO₂, and after application in *in vitro* studies, the ability to self-control hyperthermia under an alternating magnetic field without cytotoxicity is showed. Additionally, this study showed the effect on the ability to improve mineralization of osteoblasts, as well as suggested an interesting strategy for application in bone tumours, ensuring the safety of the hyperthermic effect [187,270]. Other conducted study indicated that by combining bioactive glass (BG) scaffolds functionalized with CuFeSe₂ nanocrystals (BG-5CFs) with NIR laser the temperature was increased. This phenomenon induced the ablation of saos-2 cells and consequently reduction of tumour *in vivo* was observed. Good cell adhesion, proliferation and osteogenic differentiation of rBMSCs and bone regeneration *in vivo* was also obtained [157] (Fig. 8B). Developing a magnetic hydrogel integrated with chemotherapy drugs offers a promising strategy for tumor treatment. Zhao and coauthors developed an injectable bifunctional magnetic-thermal chemotherapeutic hydrogel platform designed for bone tumor therapy. The system encapsulates iron oxide (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles, biocompatible mediators for magnetothermal energy conversion, and the chemotherapy drug doxorubicin (DOX) within a magnetic alginate hydrogel (DOX@MAH). This hydrogel exhibits exceptional adaptability to complex bone shapes and rapidly forms a gel upon contact with calcium ions. Following tumor resection, DOX@MAH can be injected into bone defect areas, where it reacts with calcium ions to solidify and fill irregular resection margins. Leveraging its synergistic magnetothermal and chemotherapeutic properties, the hydrogel delivers localized, long-lasting, and highly efficient tumor cell eradication, significantly reducing the likelihood of recurrence [271].

The regenerative cascade or the evaluation of therapeutic effect against a tumour can be improved by the incorporation of magnetic cells into the scaffold. Magnetic cells can be labelled with magnetic nanoparticles through cells surface integrin or by internationalization (i.e. through fluid phase endocytosis, receptor-mediated endocytosis or phagocytosis) [272]. Magnetic cells can be combined with external magnetic fields. This mechanism allowed to conduct the cells to a specific target and to control the delivery of biomolecules, drugs, growth factors, or tracers for diagnosis or to be used in target therapy, as cancer therapy by conjugation with antibodies (e.g. tumour growth inhibition), as well as can be used to improve the hyperthermia effect [264,267]. This mechanism is non-toxic and do not affect cell differentiation, proliferation, metabolic expression profile, reactive oxygen species formation and apoptosis rate [152,174,263]. Magnetic cells can be incorporated into the scaffold and the scaffold resorption can be follow-up and monitored by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [61,161,174,273,274]. As an example, Zhang and coauthors, develop stem cell spheroids for MRI tracking and bone regeneration. Bone marrow stem cells (BMSCs), labelled with modified iron oxide nanoparticles (IONPs), were incorporated into a GelMA/PAM hydrogel platform to create magnetically labelled stem cell spheroids. IONP-labelled spheroids showed excellent cellular viability, forming intricate network structures rich in ECM proteins, and were successfully imaged using MRI *in vitro*. *In vivo* experiments confirmed the biosafety of IONP-labelled spheroids in an animal model of alveolar bone defects,

enabling MRI observation and significantly accelerating bone defect regeneration [275].

On the other hand, it is imperative to develop advanced theranostic scaffolds capable in one way to treat the bone tumor and in another way to be used as a tool for visualizing bone regeneration while actively promoting bone repair. Scaffolds would provide invaluable, real-time insights into the healing process, enabling the optimization of scaffold design for enhanced therapeutic outcomes. A multifunctional scaffold designed for simultaneous osteogenic stimulation and non-invasive monitoring of bone regeneration was developed using a hard-and-soft integration strategy. The scaffold combines 3D-printed microfilaments with a hydrogel network containing simvastatin (SV), indocyanine green-loaded superamphiphiles, and aminated ultrasmall superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (USPIO-NH₂). Controlled SV release significantly enhances osteogenesis, as demonstrated by *in vitro* and *in vivo* results. The scaffold also enables near-infrared II fluorescence imaging responsive to alkaline phosphatase and scaffold degradation monitoring via MRI [276].

A magnetic bone-like scaffold was engineered composed of collagen and hydroxyapatite, functionalized with magnetic nanoparticles (SPIONs) for *in vivo* monitoring during bone regeneration. Two strategies were employed for SPION integration: naked SPIONs (nMNPs) and coated SPIONs (MNPs) with carboxylic acid groups enabling covalent attachment to collagen. The scaffolds were characterized for morphology, crystallinity, and stability, and MRI analyses, along with radiotracer uptake evaluations, confirmed their imaging potential. *In vitro* cell proliferation assays showed no cytotoxicity from the SPIONs. Results indicated that incorporating SPIONs during scaffold synthesis achieved a more uniform distribution. This approach offers a biocompatible material for bone regeneration while enabling non-invasive, long-term monitoring of healing progress via imaging techniques [277].

Magnetic materials are set to become innovative tools in revolutionizing bone tissue regeneration, cancer treatment, non-invasive monitoring of cell interaction, scaffold degradation and bone formation, offering enhanced precision, efficacy, and versatility in therapeutic applications.

6. Conclusions and future perspectives

Researchers have been investigated possible solutions that can mimic the native tissues aiming to reduce the inflammatory response and simultaneously to promote tissue regeneration. Based on recent research, and as an indicative roadmap for future research, biomimicry (by a compositional, structural, and mechanical perspective) is considered a target-material for scientists, as it is evident that in such conditions the cell response is closer to the natural behaviour obtained in the presence of healthy tissues. From macro to micro scale, hydroxyapatite based-materials, scaffolds and nature inspired strategies are reported. On the other hand, an in-lab bio-inspired biomineralization process was investigated as a promising process to obtain biomimetic and multifunctional biomaterials. Natural based materials can be mineralised with multiple ions-doped hydroxyapatite that showed interesting biochemical, biological, morphological, suitable mechanical and magnetic properties, exhibiting physicochemical and ultrastructural mimesis with natural tissues. Among the possible physical, non-destructive stimulation mechanisms, magnetic forces are very interesting to impart specific signalling to cells and drive specific biologic and bio-functional effects. Fe-HA and Fe-HA based materials are relevant examples of biomaterial matching biomimicry and functional (magnetic) ability.

In bone related-diseases various challenges are addressed including the reduction of inflammatory process, reduction of unhealthy cells, as well as to promote tissue regeneration. As described in this review, osteosarcoma and osteoporosis are defined as worldwide concern, due to affect young and elderly people, respectively. High costs are implemented to define efficient treatments, however until now, non-effective

treatments are showed. The future perspective includes defining innovative solutions that effectively meet the needs of bone-related diseases. For example, by replicating the native tissue structure from the nano to macro scale, novel solutions can be developed to recruit endogenous cells, modulate the immune environment, and promote tissue regeneration. The potential of bio-inspired biomineralization processes enables the development of biomimetic materials through natural matrices nucleated with multi-ion-doped hydroxyapatite. In the case of osteosarcoma, is hypothesised that the development of novel biomimetic and magnetic scaffolds might be tailored and activated by pulsed electromagnetic fields (PEMFs). In fact, temperature might be slightly increased (40 °C), but with no side effects and can effectively eliminate the remained tumour cells without damaging the surrounding healthy tissue. Therefore, biomimetic nature of the scaffold, the precise ions position into HAp lattice, the release of ions and porous architecture, might enables cell recognition, as an endogenous tissue, as well as trigger specific immune response and emulating the regenerative cascade. On the other hand, is hypothesised that the bone fractures related osteoporosis can be reduced by developing a 3D network that mimic the native tissue, fulfil the spaces generated by the disease, and simultaneously helps on recruiting endogenous cells to support the tissue regeneration. Nevertheless, is also hypothesise that magnetic materials can be tailored with magnetic fields as a possible source of antibacterial effect, considering that a relevant role is played by electric charges on the biomaterial surface.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ana Catarina Almeida: Writing – original draft. **Diana Pacheco:** Writing – original draft. **Artur Mateus:** Resources, Funding acquisition. **Monica Montesi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Silvia Panseri:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Nuno Alves:** Resources, Funding acquisition. **Simone Sprio:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Tatiana M. Fernandes Patrício:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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